
An Analytical Study of Market Trends and Consumer Preferences for Organic and Sustainable Green Cosmetic Products with Reference to Ahilyanagar District in Maharashtra

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15111230

Abstract:

The cosmetic industry is the most popular growing industry in the modern world. The growing awareness of skincare, haircare and personal hygiene is growing day by day due to the social media experts and influencers as they are promoting and educating people through their channels. With these awareness people demand is also growing for cosmetic products especially green organic sustainable cosmetics so it has seen a paradigm shift due to rising environmental concerns and increasing consumer awareness for chemical free safe products. This study aims to analyse the market trends and consumer preferences for organic cosmetic products in Ahilyanagar. The research highlights factors responsible for demand decisions among consumers, how environmental consciousness affects people during their demand for products, how natural ingredients affect the demand for products, how changes in price affects their demand pattern in Ahilyanagar. It also shows what are the factors which are affecting the growth of sustainable organic cosmetic industry and what policy should these natural organic cosmetics industry adopt to face the growing competition by modern traditional products. The findings will provide valuable details for organic cosmetic companies to align their marketing strategies and help new and established entrepreneur to adjust changing consumer expectations. It will also help consumers by citing out the details which the industries need to improve to benefit consumer and also organic cosmetic industry. The study is mostly confined to Ahilyanagar consumer behaviour pattern in response to green cosmetics.

Keywords: *Organic Cosmetics, Green Products, Consumer Preferences, Market Trends, Ahilyanagar.*

Introduction:

The cosmetic industry is the most attracting industry getting lots of attention in the modern day world. It has grabbed attention of all the ages especially between 15 to 50 age groups people, especially women's have a high demand for cosmetic products but we have even seen the male population becoming aware due to ongoing Instagram, Facebook channels and pages which promote and educate regarding the skincare, grooming and personal hygiene, so this has even led to significant transformation due to the growing demand for eco-friendly organic cosmetic products as people are attracted towards natural products and not chemically made modern medical products. Consumers are becoming more aware of the harmful effects of chemical-based cosmetics, leading to a shift towards organic and sustainable options. This study aims to explore the consumer preferences for green cosmetics and it also studies their demand pattern for organic natural cosmetic brands in Ahilyanagar. The study also makes analysis of what are the future growth possibilities for sustainable organic cosmetic industries and it also provides recommendations for future growth of organic cosmetic industries.

Problems:

- Limited availability of green cosmetic products due to less brands entering this market of natural cosmetic and than problem of availability of most of natural cosmetic brands in local store and beauty stores.
- Misinformation regarding product authenticity and quality regarding their effectiveness and less variety in terms of products in comparison to traditional products.
- Less effective providing instant results than the chemical based products.

Objectives:

1. To analyze the consumer behavior for organic and sustainable cosmetics in Ahilyanagar.
2. To study consumer preferences and demand for green cosmetic products in Ahilyanagar.
3. To evaluate the challenges faced by consumers in purchasing green cosmetics products in Ahilyanagar
4. To provide recommendations for promoting green cosmetic products

Scope of the Study:

The study focuses on consumers residing in Ahilyanagar and highlights the current and future scenario of consumers purchase regarding organic and sustainable cosmetic products in Ahilyanagar district. The research includes both male and female consumers aged between 15-50 above years. The research will highlight the importance of green cosmetics and how the green organic cosmetics have brought a new trend among the consumers. It will even provide a deep insights for the firms who wish to enter in this green cosmetic industry. The study also provides future growth recommendations for the improvement of the green cosmetic firms and provide suggestions for them on how to raise the demand for their products and build confidence regarding their product quality among the consumers. The study will be essential for both buyer and firms in Ahilyanagar district and even out of the district any general area in order to make a decision as it provides good depth about the organic green cosmetic.

Limitations:

While this research provides valuable insights into market trends and consumer preferences for organic and sustainable green cosmetic products in Ahilyanagar district, it has certain limitations that must be acknowledged.

One of the primary limitations is the **geographical scope** of the study. Since the research is confined to Ahilyanagar district, the findings may not be fully representative of the larger state or national market. Consumer preferences and market trends may vary significantly across different regions due to cultural, economic, and environmental factors, limiting the generalizability of the results.

Another constraint is the **sample size and respondent diversity**. Although efforts are made to include a diverse group of consumers, the sample may not capture the full spectrum of opinions and behaviors.

Moreover, **self-reported data** from surveys and interviews may introduce bias, as respondents may provide socially desirable answers rather than their true preferences or behaviors. Additionally, **market dynamics in the cosmetic industry are constantly evolving**, influenced by new product innovations, regulatory changes, and shifting consumer awareness, making it difficult to capture long-term trends within a limited research period. Despite these limitations, the study offers a strong foundation for understanding regional consumer behavior and provides insights for further research in the organic cosmetics industry.

Data Collection:

The data for this study is collected through both **primary and secondary sources** to ensure a comprehensive analysis. **Primary data** is gathered using structured questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions. Surveys are conducted among consumers to assess their preferences, awareness, and purchasing behaviour. **Secondary data** is obtained from industry reports, government publications, research journals, and market analysis studies on organic and sustainable cosmetics. This combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods ensures a well-rounded understanding of consumer behavior and market dynamics in Ahilyanagar district.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology for this study, *An Analytical Study of Market Trends and Consumer Preferences for Organic and Sustainable Green Cosmetic Products with Reference to Ahilyanagar District in Maharashtra*, is designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the evolving consumer behavior and market dynamics in this sector. To achieve this, the study employs a combination of both descriptive and analytical research approaches. The descriptive aspect aims to map the existing trends and consumer preferences, while the analytical approach delves deeper into the factors influencing the demand for organic and sustainable green cosmetics.

A mixed-methods approach is adopted to ensure a well-rounded and insightful analysis. This includes both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The quantitative research primarily focuses on gathering statistical data related to consumer behavior, market share, and product preferences. Meanwhile, the qualitative aspect involves exploring consumer motivations, perceptions, and barriers to adoption through detailed interactions with stakeholders.

To ensure a diverse and representative sample, a purposive and stratified random sampling method is employed. The sample population consists of different consumer groups, retailers, and manufacturers associated with organic and sustainable green cosmetics. The study surveys 76 respondents, which includes 24 per students, 14.7 per business professional, 24 per self employed and 36 per from many random profession. This ensures that perspectives from both the demand and supply sides of the market are incorporated, thereby providing a holistic view of the industry.

For data collection, the study relies on both primary and secondary sources. Primary data is collected through structured questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions. A well-formulated questionnaire, containing close-ended questions is designed to assess consumer preferences, awareness levels, brand loyalty, and purchasing behavior in Ahilyanagar. Focus group discussions further enhance the understanding of consumer attitudes and perceptions regarding eco-friendly beauty products.

Additionally, secondary data is gathered from market reports, government publications, research journals. Insights from global and regional cosmetic market research firms also contribute to the contextual understanding of market trends. By integrating these multiple sources, the study ensures the reliability and validity of its findings.

The collected data is then analyzed using various statistical and qualitative techniques. Quantitative data is processed through statistical tools such as Mean, Median and correlation analysis to identify key trends and correlations. Descriptive statistics help in summarizing data points such as percentages and frequency distributions, while inferential statistics such as regression analysis are applied to determine the relationships between variables like age, income, environmental awareness, and purchase decisions. Qualitative data, on the other hand, is analyzed thematically to identify common consumer sentiments, motivations, and concerns. Content

analysis is also employed to extract meaningful insights from interview responses and open-ended survey answers.

While the study provides valuable insights into the organic and sustainable green cosmetic market in Ahilyanagar, it is important to acknowledge its scope and limitations. As the research is confined to a specific district, the findings may not be fully generalizable to the broader state or national market. However, the study serves as an important reference point for understanding regional consumer behaviour and can be used to guide marketing strategies, policy recommendations, and further research in this field. Through this methodology, the research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the growing shift towards eco-friendly and sustainable beauty products in the modern consumer landscape.

Discussion and results:

The study included population of all ages which included age groups 15 -25, 26-35, 36-45 and above from Ahilyanagar district. Total 76 people were included in the study and their responses were collected through questionnaire which included both male and females. Among the respondents there were some students, business professionals, homemakers, self employed and also from many other more profession. Their monthly income was also taken into consideration. Their responses revealed that 81.6% people were aware of organic and sustainable green products, which shows that people are aware and known to the environmental friendly cosmetic products. Among them 59.2 per revealed that they prefer natural cosmetic products, very few preferred chemically made cosmetic products, 26.3 per preferred both organic and chemical products and 7.9 people didn't prefer any use of any cosmetic products.

The study also showcases which green cosmetic products were mostly demanded, it showed that 29.3 per people mostly demand skincare products like creams and lotions, 18.7 per demanded for haircare like shampoos and oils and 45.1 per people demand all kinds of green cosmetic products. The researcher also questions regarding the performance level of green cosmetic products it showed that 60.8 per were satisfied with their performance and 35.1 % had neutral view on it and also very minimal remaining people were not impressed by the performance of green organic cosmetic.

The questionnaire also included question regarding what are the exact reason behind so many people choosing green cosmetics so it was found that 39.7 % used because they wanted natural chemical free products, 42.5 per demanded due to health consciousness and 16.4 percent preferred green cosmetics as they had awareness regarding environmental concerns. Among the overall respondent 89.7 % found that green cosmetics were useful for tackling problems like acne, baldness which showed that it has potential to deal with this concerns as like traditional cosmetics brands but 10.7 per found that it was not very useful in dealing with acne baldness like issues so it seems that green cosmetics industries still have to work to tackle this issues in order to compete with traditional brands which provide complete solutions to this issues.

Participants also gave insights about the price that the natural organic cosmetic brands were mostly of high cost, their availability was also less and most of them provided misleading labels by providing fake promises by promoting their products to be natural and sustainable. 14.9 per people said that they did not face any challenges while purchasing the green cosmetic products. Price and brand reputation play a significant role in purchasing decisions. However, the higher cost of green cosmetics acts as a barrier for many consumers. Brands like Mamaearth, Biotique, and Plum and many more are among the most preferred natural cosmetics brands consumers demand in Ahilyanagar.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that there is a growing demand for organic and sustainable green cosmetic products in Ahilyanagar. People are aware of how much they can benefit from the use of natural skin care products in getting good skin in the district. Chemical products do provide good effect but have negative impacts on the people having sensitive skin and also the harmful chemical have changes of getting absorbed in the blood stream and have carcinogenic properties which is actually creating fear among the population and leading them to shift on the natural cosmetic brands. All people are getting aware about the environmental concern and how eco-friendly and environmental friendly cosmetics can put sustainable and good impact on earth. The research shows that more than 59.2 % people choose organic products over chemical. This gives a positive hope to make profit to entrepreneurs who are planning to enter natural cosmetic market, they have a high chance of making profit, as we can see there is high demand for organic cosmetic in Ahilyanagar district by this analysis we can even draw a relatable connections of situation with other districts being same too. The people who don't wish to shift on complete organic have certain issues regarding less variety in natural cosmetic brands and less brands providing quick effects on the concerning skin care problems. The research also shows that most of the brands are misleading in the name of being natural which is why some people are abstaining from buying it, the transparency in production process and ingredients list can increase more demand and more preference for the green products in the district. Most of the green and organic cosmetic products are made from food grains like milk, fruits and vegetables which can even generate more income for farmers as the demand for the natural products among consumers will increase, so this study provides the exact conditions of demand pattern and consumers behaviour towards organic cosmetic products in the district. However, price sensitivity is also the issue for some people due to the higher prices of organic cosmetic products the study has shown people being extremely sensitive to price. Cosmetic companies need to adopt competitive pricing strategies and promote product authenticity to increase consumer trust.

Recommendations:**Conduct awareness campaigns:**

By conducting awareness campaign about the benefits of green cosmetics, it will lead to positive psychological impacts among the masses in order to purchase more organic green cosmetics and during the campaign influencers should highlight the important of how the organic green cosmetic are environmental friendly and cruelty free. During the testing of cosmetic suitability for human, animals are tested so awareness campaigns must highlight that organic cosmetic products don't harm animals and are good to nature which can build empathy among the buyers for being responsible to nature and lead to more demand of organic cosmetic products.

Provide trial packs:

By providing trial packs customers can use it and understand the quality of the products to build faith by spending their own money. Most of the consumers have sensitive skin which always makes a doubt in their mind whether the product will suit so by offering free trials the buyers get confidence in the product quality and suitability. It can also enable long term demand and built credibility among the population to buy organic cosmetics.

Collaborate with beauty influencers for promotions:

Nowadays there are lot more good instagram, facebook, youtube and various social media influencers who educate and aware people on the lifestyle related aspects, so organic cosmetic brand owners should collaborate with the good influencer or dermatologist channel who will

promote the organic cosmetic brands which will make people aware of it and enhance the demand for the product.

Ensure proper certification and labelling of organic products:

The producer should mention proper certification and also label their products properly. Most of the times companies provide less or no information of ingredients list and also other details about the product which lead to lose confidence regarding the product among consumer, so people think that company is keeping lots of aspects misleading by not being transparent and that can lead to fall in demand. so company should label and highlight proper details to enhance and raise demand and awareness regarding cosmetic products.

Introduce loyalty programs for regular customers:

Organic natural brands should offer various schemes like buy one get one free or discount prices or coupons to their regular customers in order to maintain brand loyalty. This will help them to keep constant demand in the long run.

References:

1. Hailes, Julia. *The New Green Consumer Guide*. Simon & Schuster, 2007.
2. Banbury, Catherine, Robert Stinerock, and Saroja Subrahmanyam. "Sustainable Consumption: Introspecting Across Multiple Lived Cultures." *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 65, no. 4, 2012, pp. 497-503.
3. Miniero, Giulia, et al. "Being Green: From Attitude to Actual Consumption." *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, vol. 38, no. 5, 2014, pp. 521-528.
4. Pinto, Diego Costa, et al. "Going Green for Self or for Others? Gender and Identity Salience Effects on Sustainable Consumption." *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, vol. 38, no. 5, 2014, pp. 540-549.
5. Connolly, John, and Andrea Prothero. "Green Consumption: Life-Politics, Risk and Contradictions." *Journal of Consumer Culture*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2008, pp. 117-145.
6. Elliott, Rebecca. "The Taste for Green: The Possibilities and Dynamics of Status Differentiation Through 'Green' Consumption." *Poetics*, vol. 41, no. 3, 2013, pp. 294-322.
7. Ertz, Myriam, et al. "Exploring Pro-Environmental Behaviors of Consumers: An Analysis of Contextual Factors, Attitude, and Behaviors." *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 69, no. 10, 2016, pp. 3971-3980.
8. Goworek, Helen. "Social and Environmental Sustainability in the Clothing Industry: A Case Study of a Fair Trade Retailer." *Social Responsibility Journal*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2011, pp. 74-86.
9. Haws, Kelly L., et al. "Seeing the World Through GREEN-Tinted Glasses: Green Consumption Values and Responses to Environmentally Friendly Products." *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, vol. 24, no. 3, 2014, pp. 336-354.
10. Peattie, Ken. "Green Consumption: Behavior and Norms." *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, vol. 35, 2010, pp. 195-228.